
DECISION-MAKING STRATEGIES AND REPUTATION BY THE REGENCY OF TULUNGAGUNG IN MAINTAINING COMMUNITY ECONOMIC STABILITY DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT: *Strategic leadership is focused on determining organizational policies and goals. In terms of leadership, a leader must provide a sense of security to the community in any condition. The COVID-19 pandemic has affected many aspects of people's lives. As a result, the virus has an impact on social, economic, and other important activities. What most people feel is the difficulty of meeting their daily needs due to the declining economic system. Of course, this is the responsibility of the government in providing solutions in overcoming the problems that arise due to COVID-19, including the Tulungagung Regency government which is also facing this outbreak. Through qualitative studies, namely reviews of books, journals, other important documents, official government news, and private media news, Therefore, to realize this, various strategies will be carried out that will produce strategic policies related to the economy whose aim is to meet the needs of the community and Regent Regulation No. 5 of 2020 to bring order to the community and comply with health protocols. The good reputation of Tulungagung Regency also plays an important role in providing the best service to the community.*

KEYWORDS: *Strategy, Economic Stability, Covid-19.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Leadership is a set of arts, abilities, and processes for influencing certain people to carry out a series of joint activities according to the vision and mission that has been made. In practice, leadership must be strategic to deal with all the dynamics of an ever-changing and stressful environment. Therefore, the term strategic leadership is known. Strategic leadership is a trait that is not just art about the preparation, implementation, and evaluation of decisions, but how a leader-spirited person can bring the masses to achieve his vision and mission. Strategic leadership focuses on the process of how a leader's formula can lead to the formulation, development policy, and mobilization to achieve goals, and allocate resources to implement policies and achieve organizational goals.

Regarding leadership, each leader has his or her distinctive style in leading a group. Organizations need a leader who is smart and wise because leading an organization is not as easy as turning the palm, especially if the organization is inhabited by heterogeneous individuals. In today's global era, the relevance of strategic leadership is to realize the goals of society Indonesia, namely people's welfare and better survival, can feel safe and peaceful in their own country.

The context of realizing a sense of security for humanity or society is very clearly contained in the 1945 Constitution, which states that the state protects the entire Indonesian nation and all of its bloodshed. This means that the values that have been formulated by the founding fathers of the nation have existed and become the wisdom of the past life of the ancestors of the Indonesian nation. In addition, the other side that is most important is to maintain integrity, Pancasila is a source of legal footing because in a very diverse life it is felt that it will lead to a direction that is humane and fair.

Today everyone realizes that the world, including Indonesia, is experiencing a tough test with the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic everywhere. This epidemic has affected many aspects of life. Upheaval occurs everywhere due to restrictions on social, economic, and other activities to protect themselves from the transmission of the virus. The impact that is most felt is the people who are starting to find it difficult to meet their needs because their economic fields have stopped. Based on this the government's policy is to overcome the difficulties of the community. Both the central and regional governments agreed to provide the best formula to overcome the epidemic for the sake of community resilience.

Tulungagung Regency is one of the areas most affected by the COVID-19 outbreak. This area with the jargon "Ayem Tentrem Mulyo lan Tinoto" gave a good response to the weakening situation and conditions. Various strategic policies are given by the government to maintain the wheels of people's lives. Collaborating with relevant regional agencies such as the TNI, POLRI, and mass organizations is the hallmark of this district. The awareness that arises whether or not an area will progress is based on how strategic the decisions are and what reputations must be maintained.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Strategy

Strategy is a planning pattern that combines goals, policies, and a series of activities into a unified whole to achieve predetermined organizational goals (Avianti, 2015). Meanwhile, according to Mintzberg, the notion of strategy is divided into five forms known as the 5 P, namely planning (plan), pattern (pattern), position (position), perspective (perspective), and game or tactics (play). The following is an explanation of the 5 Ps, including:

a. Strategy is planning

The concept of strategy cannot be separated from aspects of planning, direction, or reference for the company's steps to achieve future goals. However, strategy is not always planning for the future. This is because strategy also involves everything that has been done before.

b. Strategy is a pattern

Strategy is a pattern, hereinafter referred to as intended strategy and so-called, because it has not been implemented and is future-oriented, but is also referred to as a realized strategy when the strategy has been carried out by the company.

c. Strategy a position

In this case, the strategy is positioning, namely positioning certain products into certain markets. Strategy as a position according to Mintzberg tends to look down, namely to a single point of view, where certain products meet with customers and look outside, namely reviewing various aspects of the external environment.

d. Strategy is perspective

If in the second and third P, they tend to look down and out, on the contrary, in the strategic perspective, they tend to look more inward, namely into the organization and up, namely to see the main vision of the company.

e. Strategy is a game

Strategy is a game is a maneuver to outwit an opponent or competitor. A brand, for example, launches a second brand, so that its position remains strong and untouched because competing brands will be busy fighting against the second brand (Sinaga, 2016).

2.2 Definition of Decision Making

In analyzing a decision, a leader is more focused on formulating and solving problems, but first, he must know the problem. A good leader must have the ability to identify problems and opportunities early. Decisions are the beginning of all conscious and directed human activities, both individually, in groups, and institutionally. So, whoever wants a certain activity he must be able and dare to make decisions related to it as precisely as possible. Decisions are aimed at the future, the results will be useful in the days to come.

Experts have various views on the meaning of this decision-maker, namely:

- a. George R. Terry in his book *Salusu* explains, the definition of a decision as "a decision is a conclusion reached after consideration, it occurs when one option is selected, to the exclusion of other". occurs after one possibility is selected while conveying another (Salusu, 1996).
- b. H. Malayu SP Hasibuan said that decision-making is a process of determining a good decision from some alternatives to carry out activities in the future (Hasibuan, 2007).
- c. Praji Atmosudirjo cited in his book *Surharnan* that a decision is an ending rather than a thought process about a problem by choosing an alternative (Suharman, 2005).

Based on From some of the definitions above, it can be concluded that decision making is a process of how to determine the best, logical, rational, and ideal decisions based on facts, data, and information from some alternatives to achieve the goals that have been set with the smallest risk, effectively, and efficiently to be implemented. in the future.

2.3 Decision Making Base

Based on taking decisions made by leaders are usually based on beliefs, intuition (conscience), facts, experience (experience), and power (authority). The explanation is as follows:

a. Confidence

Leaders in their decision-making are based on the belief that this decision is the best after taking into account and analyzing internal and external factors as well as the positive and negative impacts of the decision. So, belief is used as the basis for decision-making.

b. Intuition

Leaders in making decisions are based on their conscience are inspired and their feelings. Goals, influences, preferences, and individual psychological decision-making play an important role. This intuitive decision-making is unconsciously influenced by past knowledge, practice, and background. Usually, he is an activist, dynamic, and always asks questions about situations and finds solutions to difficult problems. Intuitive decision-making usually relies on instinct, personal feelings, mental abilities, but every situation is faced with a realistic attitude and decides according to feelings only.

c. Facts

Decision-making is based on the results of the analysis of data, information, and facts that are often used by the ability of imagination, experience, the right perspective, and the power of thinking to implement future situations and conditions. In this case, the leader should not be a complete robot analyzing data, information, and facts. Decisions made based on these facts are relatively good, logical, rational, and accountable and can be applied to every situation and condition.

d. Experience

Leaders in making decisions are based on their experiences and the experiences of others. Experience is invaluable, providing clues and providing answers to questions that should be done in these situations and conditions.

e. Power

The Decision-maker in making his decision must be guided by the power he has so that the decision is valid and legal to enforce. This is due to the authority. Included in decision-making are individual decisions and group decisions. An individual decision is that this decision is only determined by a manager, while subordinates can only participate in providing suggestions, opinions, and information, but are not entitled to

participate in deciding it. Meanwhile, group decisions are decisions made by group members, both based on the results of consensus and deliberation, as well as voting. In the decision-making process, group members play an active role in discussing the objectives of the decision, the risks, and the impact of the decision and participate in determining the decision (Hasibuan, 2007).

2.4 Reputation Concept

Reputation is one of the most important elements in the world of government because a good or bad reputation is an important indicator of success. Reputation is a complex thing, but if managed properly will be very valuable. Fajrina (2012) said that reputation is the embodiment of a person's experience with the product or service they get. A good reputation will increase credibility, make people more confident, and will get what they have been promised. Reputation is a guarantee that people will get something according to their expectations.

Following the explanation above, the simple conclusion is that reputation is the public's perception of the government which depends on what the government does as an entity. Furthermore, the government's reputation indicators are one of the guidelines for the community in making assessments. Reputation itself can be ranked as good, moderate, or bad. A bad reputation gives birth to a negative impact on the government's operational system, while on the contrary if a good reputation will give birth to a positive transformation to the public. The following are reputation indicators, namely:

a. Good name

A good name is the public's perception of the extent of the progress of the government. Maintaining a good name is certainly one of the main obligations to support the smooth running of the system.

b. Reputation of other regions

The reputation of other regions is the public's perception of other regions in some government performance. A government must have the power to highlight its superior value compared to other regions where it means that characteristics are needed.

c. Widely known

Widely known shows the perception of the extent to which it is widely known by the public.

d. Then remember

Ease of remembering shows the perception of the ease of remembering the good name of an area (Sutojo, 2004).

2.5 Economic Stability

Economic stability is the purpose of the process of economic stabilization. Economic stability is important to encourage the achievement of community welfare through economic growth and improving the quality of life. This can be achieved if all economic variables are in a balanced condition (Windasari, 2020). The success of efforts to stabilize the economy is marked by the development of economic activity as evidenced by the improvement in stable fiscal and monetary conditions.

Economic stability is a basic prerequisite for the achievement of improving people's welfare and improving the quality of growth. An unstable economy creates high costs for the economy and society. Instability will make it difficult for the community, both private and household, to plan for the future, especially in the longer-term required for investment. A low level of investment will reduce the potential for long-term economic growth.

2.6 Covid-19

Covid-19 according to the World Health Organization (WHO) is a very dangerous epidemic and has infected almost all countries of the world. Covid-19 is a contagious outbreak caused by a coronavirus. Coronavirus, which was first discovered in Wuhan, China, is a group of viruses that cause disease in animals and humans (www.who.int/indonesia/news, 2020). This virus can attack anyone through the air or physical contact, some people are infected with symptoms, but some who look healthy are also infected. Since the

discovery of this disease, which has been around for a year, Indonesia has just announced the arrival of an officially imported vaccine from China that can ward off or fight the virus from COVID-19.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this study, researchers used a qualitative approach with descriptive analysis methods through data collection which was described in detail and regularly. Data collection techniques through documentation are carried out through reviewing and/or browsing several books, journals, printed or electronic documents, and other sources of data or information deemed relevant to the research or study (Supriyadi, 2016).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 The Concept of Decision Making Strategy by the Regent in Maintaining Community Economic Stability During the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Based on the results of the study, researchers found the fact that based on data from the East Java government, the Tulungagung area was the part affected by the COVID-19 outbreak. Knowing this, the Tulungagung district government made various efforts quickly and swiftly. The decision that received positive signals from various elements of society was the implementation of Regent Regulation No. 55 of 2020 concerning the Violation of Health Protocols. In the law it is explained that the Tulungagung government urges its people to apply a disciplined and healthy lifestyle, if there is a violation, law enforcement sanctions will be given according to applicable regulations.

Through this Regent's Regulation, the people of Tulungagung district must apply discipline to health protocols (prokes), if they do not want to get sanctions. Especially when leaving the house, it is mandatory to follow the 3M rules, namely wearing masks, maintaining distance, and always washing hands. The sanctions for violators of health protocols are following Regent Regulation No. 55 of 2020 article 7, four sanctions will be accepted, whether violators from individuals or business actors or managers. The first is a sanction in the form of a verbal warning or written warning, the second is social work in the form of cleaning public facilities, the third is the temporary suspension of business operations and the fourth is the revocation of a business license. The sanctions were carried out by the Civil Service Police in coordination with the Tulungagung Police and the Kodim.

Maryoto Birowo as the Regent of Tulungagung hopes that the community will not be anxious about the existence of the Regent Regulation, because the purpose of the Regent Regulation is precisely to maintain the safety and security of the community. Sanctions are only given to those who violate the health protocols that have been socialized and explained to the public (Trisdianto, 2020). In addition to tightening the health protocol rules, the Tulungagung district government also has other policies, such as providing free rapid and swab tests, as well as packages of necessities and money for underprivileged families affected by the virus.

Regarding the free rapid and swab tests, Tulungagung itself became the first region to enforce the regulation. The head of the local Health Office, dr. Kasil Rokhmad stated that residents should not be afraid to check themselves if they feel they have been close to or in contact with people who have tested positive for COVID-19. He added that people should care about their health and those of those around them (www.andikafm.com, 2020). In addition to free checking and tracing by local health officers, the Tulungagung government also provides an isolation place for residents who are detected positive for COVID-19. The free rapid and swab tests are very helpful for the community. Because in other areas it is necessary to spend a lot of money just to do this. So, people save more money and can be diverted for other needs.

Furthermore, to maintain the stability of the community's economy, a very appropriate policy was taken by the local government, namely the provision of assistance. Tulungagung Regent Drs. Maryoto Birowo, MM, who was accompanied by the Head of the Welfare Section of the Regional Secretariat of Tulungagung Regency, the Head of Public Relations and Protocol of the Regional Secretariat of Tulungagung Regency, and the Secretary of Public Works Department of Highways and Human Settlements Office (Dinas PUBMCK) of Tulungagung

Regency assisted underprivileged residents in some sub-districts in the Tulungagung Regency area (section protocol.tulungagung.go. en, 2020).

The aims and objectives of the assistance are to ease the burden of suffering and the economy of disadvantaged communities in the Tulungagung Regency area. The assistance provided by the Regent of Tulungagung to the residents included necessities and money. The regent's message to the community when distributing aid is that residents must be sensitive to one another, if there are residents whose house conditions are dangerous, they need to be reported immediately and assistance will be provided.

4.2 Reputation Concept by the Regent in Maintaining Community Economic Stability During the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Based on the results of the research study, it is evident that the progress made by the Tulungagung district government in dealing with the problems caused by COVID-19 is very good. The area, which is known by the good name of Kota Ayem Tentrem Mulyo lan Tinoto, has succeeded in proving to the public that all the policies that are being pursued are able to reduce the rate of casualties due to positive COVID-19 (nusadaily.com, 2020). Even Tulungagung is a district that has recorded the highest percentage of healing at 91%. Maryoto Birowo as the regent said that the skyrocketing recovery rate was influenced by many factors and the cooperation support of various parties. He expressed his gratitude for the hard work of all parties and urged the central government to continue implementing the health protocol rules until the epidemic was completely declared gone.

The government's positive performance brought the public's perception that the government was able to deal with the virus which was considered a problem quickly. The existence of the corona was previously considered a scourge that scared various circles, but since the positive results are shown by the authorities, people are increasingly convinced that the virus will soon disappear. So that community activities related to the economy can be immediately restored.

4.3 The Impact of the Tulungagung Community with the Regent's Policy

Based on case studies in several areas of the Tulungagung Regency, in order to overcome the decline in economic growth rates, the government makes a policy package for the community's economy. The policy packages are given directly to the community as well as the provision of service facilities through government institutions or programs. Some of the direct assistance provided to the community include:

- a. Addition of nominal PKH
- b. Addition of nominal BPNT
- c. BLT for the community
- d. Assistance for business groups experiencing a decline, for example, the MSME group, fisheries, and others.

While the assistance provided through government programs include:

- a. Pre-employment card program
- b. Electricity subsidy
- c. Health care assistance

The existence of assistance from the government does not always have a positive impact, but also a negative impact. The following are the impacts of government policies:

- a. Positive impact
 - 1) Few people can fulfill their needs
 - 2) Cheaper electricity
 - 3) It's a little easier to get health services
 - 4) Ease of service through online
 - 5) Loosening of public administration management
 - 6) Ease and ease of banking administration
- b. Negative impact

- 1) Inequality between who is entitled to financial assistance
- 2) The cost of online/online communication is quite expensive
- 3) Misappropriation of aid funds
- 4) If aid is continuously disbursed, it is not impossible that there will be budget deficits in all ministry sectors

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the description above, the researcher can conclude that:

- a. Decision-making strategies are fundamental in determining the direction of policy to be taken, especially during urgent conditions that require the government to act quickly. The Tulungagung district government in this case is very fast and precise in taking policies in the midst of the outbreak *covid-19*. The strategic policies issued are related to the economy, the main objective of which is to meet the needs of the community through assistance, to provide free swab and rapid tests so that the community does not feel burdened, as well as the issuance of Regent Regulation No. 55 of 2020 to bring order to the community to be aware of complying with health protocols.
- b. The good reputation brought by the Tulungagung district provides motivation to provide the best service for its people. Many achievements must be maintained in order to remain an area that is known and proud. In addition, high public expectations of the government that must keep promises, make the government work extra hard in seeking public welfare.
- c. The impact caused by decision-making in the form of policies to maintain the stability of the economy of the people of Tulungagung can be positive and negative. The positive is that the community is more efficient with the assistance provided, while the negative is that there are many inequalities due to budget abuse and not being well targeted.

REFERENCE

Books and Journals:

- [1] Avianti, Yuniar. (2015). *Kompetensi Kewirausahaan: Teori Penguahan dan Aplikasi*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- [2] Fajrina, Rani Sherly. (2012). *Pengaruh Reputasi Perusahaan dan Komunikasi Word-Of-Mouth Terhadap Pembuatan Keputusan Kerja*. Jakarta: Universitas Indonesia..
- [3] Hasibuan, Malayu S.P. (2007). *Manajemen: Dasar Pengertian dan Masalah*, Edisi Revisi. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- [4] Salusu. 1996. *Pengambilan keputusan Strategi Untuk Organisasi Publik Akan Organisasi Non Profit*. Jakarta: Provindo.
- [5] Sinaga, Dearlina. (2016). *Kewirausahaan: Pedoman Untuk Kalangan Praktisi dan Mahasiswa*. Yogyakarta: Ekuilibria.
- [6] Suharman. (2005). *Psikologi Kognitif*. Surabaya: Srikandi Ghalia.
- [7] Supriyadi, S. (2016). "Komunitas Praktisi: Solusi Alternatif Berbagi Pengetahuan Antar Pustakawan". Lentera Pustaka: Jurnal Kajian Ilmu Perpustakaan, Informasi Dan Kearsipan, Vol 2, No 2, hh 85.
- [8] Sutojo, Siswanto. (2004). *Membangun Citra Perusahaan*. Jakarta: Dinar Mulya Pustaka.
- [9] Windasari dan Zainuddin S. (2020). "Analisis Kausalitas Stabilitas Perekonomian Terhadap Pengembangan Bank Syariah Menggunakan Pendekatan Vektor Error Correction Model". Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis Islam. Volume 2, Nomor 1, hh 1.

Internet:

- [1] Bupati Beri Bantuan Warga Kurang Mampu, dalam <http://bagianprotokol.tulungagung.go.id/bupati-beri-bantuan-warga-kurang-mampu/>.

- [2] Covid-19, dalam <https://www.who.int/indonesia/news>.
- [3] Deny Trisdianto, dalam <https://www.afederasi.com/news/government/penerapan-perbup-nomor-55-tahun-2020-pelanggar-prokes-siap-siap-kena-sanksi/>.
- [4] Kesembuhan Pasien Korona Tulungagung Mencapai di atas 90 persen, tertinggi se- Jatim, dalam <https://nusadaily.com/regional/kesembuhan-pasien-corona-tulungagung-di-atas-90-persen-tertinggi-se-jatim.html>.
- [5] Tulungagung gratiskan rapid dan swab, dalam http://www.andikafm.com/news/detail/27746/1/tulungagung-gratiskan-rapid-dan-swab?fbclid=IwAR3D5IOB9Yh968rEYGDS1Nf45jTG63mHM9f2ydmzUQjw5_mr96LkFg6YKUo.